

Determinants of Student's Choice towards International Universities for Higher Education in Nepal

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Publication Date: 2025/02/24

Abstract: This paper explores the factors that determine the student's choice towards the International Universities for Higher Education in Nepal. This report uses, relational research design along with the deductive methodology and quantitative research methodology for the research purpose. The "push-pull model" has been used to illustrate the theoretical framework. It investigates the relationship between independent variables (University Image, Cost of education, College Infrastructure, Programme Evaluation and Career Prospects) and dependent variable (Student's choice). A conceptual framework has been developed based on the extensive review of the relevant literature and the hypothesis derived from it. Furthermore, reliability test was done of the 130 responses collected to test the validity and effectiveness of the study. Hence, analytical tools such as descriptive and correlation were used to find out the impact and relation between variables as well as conduct hypothesis testing. Programme Evaluation, University Image and Career Prospects of the International Universities in Nepal were found to be the major factors that students looked upon while choosing universities for higher education.

Keywords: *International University, Higher Education, Student's Choice, Push-Pull Factors, Nepal.*

How to Cite: Trishna Tamang (2025). Determinants of Student's Choice towards International Universities for Higher Education in Nepal. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 10(2), 558-566. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14921226>

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of an International University Degree has been booming in Nepal although the students still prefer national universities or going abroad as in the FY 2074-75 as many as 56,216 Nepali students went abroad for higher studies – an increase of 10,000 Nepali students in comparison to the previous year (Upsurge Educational Service, 2021). Since the concept of International Degree is increasing steady, the number of private colleges providing foreign-affiliated degrees is also increasing. There are more than 20 international universities operating in Nepal as of March 2020 (Ministry of Education, Science and Technology, 2020).

Though there are private colleges in Nepal that provide foreign degrees the number of students going abroad is increasing by 17.79% each year (Edu Sanjal Pvt Ltd, 2020). The amount that Nepalese students spent in 2019 to pursue higher education had increased by 19.7% compared to 2018, reaching Rs 40.9 billion (Nepali Times, 2019). 63% of students' destination was Australia meanwhile the others are the UK, India, Japan, Cyprus, India, China, Canada, United States, New Zealand, South Korea and UAE (Nepali Times, 2019). This problem deteriorates the rate of students getting International Degrees in Nepal due to a higher influence of

the abroad study concept (Nepali Times, 2019) and drains the country's economy as billions are spent on foreign education.

The concept of an International University Degree has been booming in Nepal although the students still prefer national universities or going abroad. This problem deteriorates the rate of students getting International Degrees in Nepal due to a higher influence of the abroad study concept (Upsurge Educational Service, 2021). There are some research papers that discuss Nepalese students' motivation to study abroad or even private colleges in Nepal itself. But a very few research papers are seen which addresses the factors affecting Nepalese students' choice of foreign-affiliated colleges in Nepal. With foreign degrees now increasingly available in Nepal, it is crucial to study the factors which will affect the student's desire for such a degree in Nepal itself.

The **push and pull factor analysis** can help *To identify the factors that affect the student's choice of International Universities for higher education in Nepal*

In addition, the research aims to accomplish the following specific objectives in order to address the research questions effectively:

- To examine the association between Student's choice and **University image**
- To examine the association between Student's choice and the **Cost of education**.
- To examine the association between Student's choice and **College infrastructure**
- To examine the association between Student's choice and **Programme evaluation**.
- To examine the association between Student's choice and **Career prospects**.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *The Push-Pull Model*

The push-pull model was originally used to explain the factors influencing the migration of people (Lee, 1996). But this model in the present content is being used by educationists and researchers as a basis for the examination of the factors and motivations of students' decision-making (Wilkins and Huisman, 2015a), (María Cubillo, Sánchez and Cerviño, 2006), (Chen, 2007).

Push factors refer to student needs, wants, and desires, and these are intangible and intrinsic needs. They can initiate a student's decision to undertake study (Gatfield and Chen 2006). Examples of push factors are the desire for academic reputation, quality of the programme, period of study, an expectation of good facilities, and employment prospects, as pointed out by Maringe (2006) and Li and Bray (2007). By contrast, pull factors are associated with the attractiveness of institutional features or attributes, which are more tangible (Mazzarol and Soutar 2002; Wilkins, Balakrishnan, and Huisman 2012). Thus, pull motivational factors tend to be more external, situational, and cognitive aspects as compared to push factors, which are more intrinsic and related to internal or emotional aspects of the individual student.

This research adopts the push-pull model as its theoretical framework, as the model has been proven effective in categorising students' motivations and decision criteria in both students' choice of transnational higher education (Li, 2019, Wilkins and Huisman, 2015a, Fang and Wang, 2014, Ahmad and Buchanan, 2015, Wilkins, Balakrishnan and Huisman, 2012), and overseas education (Chen, 2007, María Cubillo, Sánchez and Cerviño, 2006, Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003, Maringe and Carter, 2007). But the focus is very much on the pull factors that drew students to study at an international university in their home country rather than the push factors that influenced Nepalese students to not study at a native university or go for abroad studies.

Various researchers have used the push and pull factors model in more advanced models to study the student's choice. Some of the factors influencing student's choice considered by (María Cubillo, Sánchez and Cerviño, 2006) are personal reasons, country and city image, institution image, and program evaluation. On the other hand Chen's model includes student characteristics (e.g., socioeconomic background, personal preferences, and academic ability) as

well as the influences of significant others (e.g., family, teachers, and employers) as the variables that influence the student's choice of International University (Chen, 2007).

Some of the push factors mentioned in the literatures (Li, 2019, Wilkins and Huisman, 2015, Fang and Wang, 2014, Ahmad and Buchanan, 2015, Wilkins, Balakrishnan and Huisman, 2012) are lack of capacity and opportunities in students' home countries, lower educational quality, employer preference for overseas education, the unavailability of particular subjects, and political and economic problems in the home countries. The pull factors most often mentioned in the literature include quality of education and reputation of country/institution, high rankings, improved employment prospects, opportunity to improve English language skills, and opportunity to experience a different culture (Wilkins and Huisman, 2015, Li, 2019).

In account to the above literature findings and the factors affecting student's choice, five independent variables are analysed in the research paper; University image, Programme Evaluation, Career Prospects, Cost of education and College infrastructure. On the basis of the conceptual framework, the following hypothesis is created:

- H1: University image is associated with Student's Choice
- H2: Cost of education is associated with the Student's Choice
- H3: College infrastructure is associated with the Student's Choice
- H4: Programme Evaluation is associated with the Student's Choice
- H5: Career Prospects is associated the Student's Choice

➤ *University Image*

Image has been defined as the impression of an organization held by both internal and external population or the views that internal members believe outsiders perceive of the organization. It can be conveyed interpersonally, through direct or indirect contact with an organization or its members (Pampaloni, 2010). One of the utmost concerns of students is university reputation, for which the ranking of a university is the most obvious measurement. The 2019 USNWR ranking involves attribute categories that include assessments by administrators at peer institutions, student retention, faculty resources, student selectivity, financial resources, alumni giving, and graduation performance. Prestigious universities are highly sought after because they offer an objective benefit in that employers use university rankings as an indication of the quality of graduates and thus prefer to recruit from among the graduates of more highly ranked universities. University prestige also provides a psychological benefit to students and their families as they have a sense of pride and satisfaction when telling others that they attend a top-ranked university.

➤ *Cost of Education*

Educational costs mean costs associated with educational programs and other expenses such as living expenses, transportation costs, tuition, books, computers, software, supplies and equipment, uniforms and other items necessary for the completion of the course work or participation in the program (Law Insider Inc., 2021). The cost of tuition is one of the top deciding factors for where students choose a college or university. Along with this the grants and scholarships provided by the college during or after the completion of their tenure also play a positive hand on the cost of education (Ahmad and Buchanan, 2015).

➤ *College Infrastructure*

Infrastructure refers to the basic physical components of a business, area or country (THE INVESTOPEDIA TEAM, 2021). And in terms of college infrastructure, includes buildings, classrooms, theatres, laboratories, sports facilities and canteens. These elements are crucial for learning environments and there has been strong evidence that good quality educational infrastructures improve the performance of students as well as improve students attraction and retention (Teixeria, Janssen; Amoroso, Jeremie; Greshman, James, 2017). And in the case of students seeking foreign degrees, they tend to look for a **state-of-art** infrastructure that matches the education quality of International Universities hence being of International standard. Being a focal point of attraction, college infrastructure also plays a crucial role in students' decision to choose International Universities in Nepal.

➤ *Programme Evaluation*

Evaluation is a methodological analysis that provides credible information which allows proper implementation of lessons learned in decision-making (Chen, 2007). Programme evaluation incorporates the pedagogy i.e. course contents and teaching/learning methods. It also includes the entire culture of the learning environment and the market-orientedness of the programme. This can include areas such as curriculum significance, skills necessary for the current job market, learning resources, physical environment, learning resources, staff attitudes, etc (Maringe and Carter, 2007). Moreover, students' selection of an International University is influenced by the institution's prestige based on the value that the programmes offered have created and social recognition. The host universities' recognition and foreign universities' recognition determine the value of the degrees (Li, 2019).

➤ *Career Prospects*

Career Prospects are defined as the probability of future employment and success in the major that is studied (Collins, 2021). And the perks of getting an international degree is that the career prospects are meant to be higher as the degrees are internationally recognized, hence higher rates of employability. Since the value of an international degree in terms of recognition is higher the career prospects are also higher. Along with these the programmes offered by

international universities includes internships, job placements and enhancing other job skills which give a boost to the careers. And for students to be able to cater a good career and get benefits in terms of employability from the college might be a point of attraction (María Cubillo, Sánchez and Cerviño, 2006).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ *Philosophical Foundation of Research*

The core of a research paper is its philosophical standing which leads the research process and allows a valid exploration of the study. Similarly, this research paper is also based on certain philosophical standings to rely on with guidelines to ascertain the validity of the research activities and get authentic results.

Since the study supposed that the push-pull factors and student choice are observable phenomena (i.e. truth is independent of human interpretation) and can be directly measured with predefined tools. This depicts that it followed the objectivist ontological dimension, with a positivist epistemological stand. In addition, for the methodology aspects, a deductive approach with quantitative methods was used to test the push-pull model with regard to student choice.

➤ *Research Design*

For this research **deductive methodology** is used in order to find the factors that impact the student's choice of International University based on the findings of the prior researchers. Since primary research will be conducted and will be analysed with statistical tools, the **quantitative research approach** will be used as it is easy to use and understand for data collection.

Based on the research objective, the relation between independent variables, 1) University Image, 2) Cost of education, 3) College Infrastructure, 4) Programme Evaluation and 5) Career Prospects and dependent variable, Student's choice needs to be identified. In order to find the association between the independent variables and dependent variable and identify the degree of association, the **relational research design** will be used in this research.

➤ *Sample*

The study population consists of high school and college students who are currently based inside and outside Kathmandu Valley. It consists of students who are currently studying in various colleges providing foreign degrees as well as those who are studying in domestic colleges to make the responses more reasonable. The sample size for this study is 130 people which incorporates students who are currently residing inside and outside Kathmandu valley. The convenience sampling technique is used for this research and will be conducted online for efficiency and security purposes. Primary data is used in the drafting of this research paper.

Table 1 Demographics of Respondents (N=130)

Demographic Variables	Category	Sample	Percentage
Gender	Female	46	45.24
	Male	84	54.76
Current Location	Kathmandu Valley	117	88.89
	Outside Kathmandu Valley	13	11.11
Age	15-20	54	41.5
	21-25	71	54.6
	26-30	5	3.8
	31 and above	0	0

The above table consists of the summary of the demographic profile of the respondents. It can be seen that out of 130 respondents, majority of them are male acquainting of 54.76%. In addition, the sample is rather skewed towards Kathmandu Valley which means that majority of the respondents reside in Kathmandu Valley. Furthermore, approximately 96% of the respondents are aged below 26 years old who are mainly of the age of joining higher education facilities.

➤ Questionnaire

The questionnaires are developed on the basis of the literature review which is the “push and pulls” model referring to (Wilkins and Huisman, 2015a) and (Fang and Wang, 2014). The questions are divided into 3 parts with 8 different sub-sections incorporating various factors. The first part is the Socio-demographic section, the second part consists of two sub-sections, the first section addresses the students’ choice of higher education, and the second section addresses the student’s view on International Degree. The third part consists of five sub-sections which includes the questions related to the independent variables of the research paper: 1) University Image, 2) Cost of education, 3) College Infrastructure, 4) Programme Evaluation and 5) Career Prospects.

The first two parts are designed in MCQ format whereas the third part is designed in 5-point Likert Scale. The Likert scale ranges from 1 to 5 where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3= neutral, 4 = agree and 5 = strongly agree. The respondents are to answer according to their views on the questions presented.

The data were collected using online measures. Google Forms were used to collect the responses from the target sample and the collected data were analysed with the help of tools like MS Excel and SPSS.

The questionnaires were distributed via email and social media to the target sample. The collection time was 2 weeks after distribution. The collected data from Google forms were downloaded in excel format and analysed with the help of SPSS.

Descriptive Statics tools of SPSS like mean, median, frequency table and standard deviation were used to find out the core factors that clearly have a huge role in students’ choice. The correlation analysis were used to find the relationship between the dependent variable; the student’s choice and each independent variable; 1) University Image, 2) Cost of education, 3) College Infrastructure, 4) Programme Evaluation and 5) Career Prospects.

➤ Reliability, Validity and Ethics

Cronbach alpha was used to test the reliability after the collected data were filtered. Only the variables with Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient greater than 0.6 is acceptable and those with 0.8 is considered good. Upon the reliability test of the independent variables used in the research, all of them had Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient greater than 0.6 which shows that all the used variables are reliable.

The variables used for this research were used in many journal articles (Sojkin, Bartkowiak and Skuza, 2012), (Fang and Wang, 2014) and (Li, 2019) where the researchers were able to find the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Variables were already tested for reliability and validated by the researchers which shows that the variables used for this research paper are also valid.

The data for the research purpose were collected only upon the consent of the responder. No personal information and identification were asked due to privacy concerns. The collected data are solely used for educational and research purposes.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Using various tools like descriptive analysis, reliability test and correlation analysis, association between demographic characteristics, dependent variables and independent variables are tested. It includes discussion on hypothesis and findings of this research paper along with the findings of the past research papers.

➤ *Descriptive Analysis*

Table 2 Descriptive Analysis of Student's Choice and Independent Variables (N=130)

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Reliability
Student's Choice	12	25	20.5462	6	-0.402	53	0.761
University Image	13	25	19.8769	8	-0.169	8	0.666
Programme Evaluation	11	20	16.4769	8	-0.308	68	0.697
Career Prospects	9	20	16.1692	8	-0.138	55	0.773
College Infrastructure	7	20	15.8846	1	-0.558	71	0.721
Cost of education	5	20	13.4	4	-0.338	25	0.836

The reliability test of both dependent and independent variables down and it was found that all the variables had Cronbach's Alpha coefficient greater than 0.66 ranging up to 0.836 which shows that all the used variables are reliable.

From the descriptive analysis of the data collected, it was found the independent variable was Programme Evaluation had the average of its data greater than the scale midpoint with negative skewness value which suggested that majority of the respondents consider that Programme Evaluation is a key factor that affects their University Choice. The University Image and Programme Evaluation was also witnessed associated with Student's Choice as the average of their data is slightly greater than the scale midpoint with negative skewness value which suggested that

the respondents consider that University Image and Career Prospects are also the factors that affect their University Choice. In addition, Cost of Education was the least influential independent variable as the average of Cost of Education data is nearly equal to the scale midpoint also with negatively skewed distribution, which showcased the fact that Cost of Education might not have higher affect the student's choice.

As all of the variables are negatively skewed it implies that most of the responses are on the higher/ left side showing that respondents agreed to the statements of the questionnaires.

➤ *Correlation Analysis*

Table 3 Spearman's rho of Student's Choice and University Image, University Image, Programme Evaluation, Career Prospects, Career Prospects, Cost of education (N=130)

Variables	Student's Choice	University Image	Programme Evaluation	Career Prospects	College Infrastructure	Cost of education
Student's Choice	1	.632**	.561**	.469**	.272**	.227**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the normality test it was found that the significance value was less than 0.5 and the ratio of skewness, which was more than 2.58, which meant that the data was not normally distributed. Hence, Spearman's rho was used for co-relation analysis with two-tailed test of significance.

The correlation analysis was done amongst five independent variables and the dependent variable i.e., student's choice. From the co-relation analysis, it is seen that University Image has a strong positive correlation with student's choice as the correlation coefficient is 0.632 which means that increase/decrease in university image would cause increase/decrease in Student's Choice. In addition, Programme Evaluation and Career prospects have a medium correlation with student choice as the correlation coefficient ranges from 0.4-0.6.

The College Infrastructure and Cost of Education has a weak correlation with Student's Choice with the lowest correlation coefficient ranging from 0.2-0.272. Among all the variables the weakest correlation is seen with Cost of Education which shows that Cost of Education has a very weak association with the Student's Choice. Hence, even though there is increase/ increase in College Infrastructure/Cost of Education, there might not be significant change in the Student's Choice.

V. FINDINGS

Data analysis revealed a range of factors that influence the student's choice of International University for higher education in Nepal. Among the variables, there is a significantly strong positive correlation (0.561) between University Image and Student's choice as found from the correlation analysis along with P-value <0.01 giving us strong evidence against null. Thus, it can be concluded that

better the University Image, more the chances students choose International University for higher education.

Hence, Hypothesis 1, University image is associated with Student’s Choice, is TRUE.

In addition, there is a moderately positive correlation (0.632) between Programme Evaluation and Student’s choice as found from the correlation analysis along with P-value <0.01, giving us strong evidence against null. Hence, it can be concluded that the high-level Programme Evaluation would improve student’s attraction towards International Universities.

Hence, Hypothesis 4, Programme Evaluation is associated with Student’s Choice, is TRUE.

A moderately positive correlation (0.469) between Career Prospects and Student’s choice can be seen from the correlation analysis along with P-value <0.01, giving us strong evidence against null. This shows that more the opportunities in terms of career prospects are provided by international universities, more likely are students to join the International Universities. Hence, Hypothesis 5, Career Prospects is associated with Student’s Choice, is TRUE.

On the other hand, there is weak correlation (0.272) between College Infrastructure and Student’s choice as found from the correlation analysis with P-value 0.002, giving us strong evidence against null. This indicates that

when the college infrastructures are improved, the students might choose the international level showing a weak association.

Hence, Hypothesis 3, College Infrastructure is associated with Student’s Choice, is TRUE.

Furthermore, Cost of Education has the weakest correlation (0.227) with Student’s choice compared to other independent variables with P-value 0.009, giving strong evidence against null. Hence, though the cost of education may increase/decrease there would be a lesser impact on the student’s choice indicating weak association.

Thus, Hypothesis 2, College Infrastructure is associated with Student’s Choice, is TRUE.

From the above hypothesis testing, three main aspects were identified as the pull factors of student’s choice: Programme Evaluation, University Image and Career Prospects.

In addition, the major push factors for student’s from joining domestic universities were low education quality of domestic institution and low level of internationalization acquainting of 46.7% and 43% of the responses as shown on Fig 2. On the other hand, the major push factors for student’s from going abroad for higher education were family influence acquainting 36.3% of the total responses as shown in Fig 3.

Fig 2 Reasons for not choosing Domestic Institution for Higher Education

Fig 3 Reasons for not going abroad for Higher Education

Furthermore, from both the descriptive and correlation analysis of the independent variable, Cost of Education, it was found that it has the least impact on the student's choice. Hence, the major findings of the data analysis are:

- Programme Evaluation has the most significant impact on Student's Choice.
- University Image and Career Prospects have moderate impact on Student's Choice.
- Cost of education has the least significant impact on Student's Choice

VI. DISCUSSION

As revealed in the literature review, most models and explanations of international student destination choice are based on the push-pull idea. But push variables had very little influence in this study mean while pull factors had significantly more power in deciding students' choice of International University. The important pull variables that influenced student decisions are Programme Evaluation, University Image and Career Prospects. The analysis of data found out that there are different levels of influence of factors for the student's choice of International Universities in Nepal. And the findings of this research may incline to the findings of the past research or have different results.

The highly influential variable as per the finding is Programme Evaluation as students are more concerned about the quality of programme offered as it plays a significant role in decision-making as found out by existing literatures (Fang and Wang, 2014) and (María Cubillo, Sánchez and Cerviño, 2006). Research have shown that the university's and program's reputation, quality, and rating to be extremely important. Another significant variable that has association with the Student's Choice is University image. Students tend to rate colleges based on their reputations rather than the actual quality of their teaching or research, therefore creating a distinct image appears to be

crucial (Marginson, 2006). The fact that potential consumers may build images of overseas branch campuses based on facts and impressions about both branch and home campuses underlines the intricacies of the image formation process (Wilkins and Huisman, 2015b).

In addition, the other influential variable was found to be Career Prospects with a moderate correlation. As found by (Sojkin, Bartkowiak and Skuza, 2012), attending a well-known, high-quality, and well-ranked university not only has a "signaling effect," but it is also thought to have a clear link to future benefits, such as greater incomes and social prestige. As a result, some students may be willing to forego a short-term financial benefit (such as the level or amount of a scholarship or assistantship) in return for better future earnings by attending a top-tier university (Sojkin, Bartkowiak and Skuza, 2012) which supports the findings that Cost of education has the least influence on the Student's choice.

VII. CONCLUSION

Until now, the research on higher education has revolved around the domestic institutions or abroad studies and no research till date has been done in order to analyse the student's choice of International Universities in Nepal. Although the interest in foreign degrees in Nepal is growing, much attention has only been given to studying the motivation of Nepali students going abroad for such a degree. In order to contribute to bridging the very gap, this research paper aims to tackle the decision-making of the prospective students. The "push-pull model" has been used to illustrate the theoretical framework. It investigates the relationship between independent variables (University Image, Cost of education, College Infrastructure, Programme Evaluation and Career Prospects) and dependent variable (Student's choice). From the analysis of 130 responses collected with tools such as descriptive and

correlation, the impact and relation between variables as well as hypothesis testing was conducted.

It was found that Programme Evaluation and University Image had higher association with the student's choice as students are more concerned about the quality of education and the prospects. Meanwhile, career prospects had a moderate relation with the student's choice which indicates that in the recent days, students are more inclined towards gaining in-hand skill and exposure that would flourish not just their educational background but also their industry readiness.

On the other hand, college infrastructure and cost of education had weak relation with student's choice which proved that student's major focus is on the quality of education and their second priority comes to the physical aspects though it is also necessary. Contrary to the findings of the other research, where cost of education played a huge role, from this survey it is seen that if the colleges can provide degrees from International Universities with excellent quality, they are ready to pay reasonable sum of money.

Hence, this study concludes that the major determinants of Student's Choice revolve around the quality of education (programme evaluation and university image) and the career prospects of an International University.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

A clear understanding of students' choice principle allows institutions to effectively position themselves in the market, thereby increasing the attractiveness of the institutions to students (Maringe and Carter, 2007). In a recently competitive marketplace of International Universities, institutions must find ways to differentiate themselves from the competition (Wilkins, Balakrishnan and Huisman, no date). In competitive markets, segmentation techniques can often be effective (Wilkins and Huisman, 2015b). Institutions that identify market segments can then focus on the segments that will help the higher education institutions achieve its strategic goals. The programme offering may then be properly positioned, with key focus on maintain a good university image and providing better career prospects. Students of various zones have varied motivations and attitudes, which influence their choice of programme selection. By focusing on the ongoing trends and catering to their specific needs, student's needs can be met more precisely. Student happiness should improve as a result of such a plan, as would student retention and word-of-mouth recommendations, all of which can contribute to student's choice of International Universities for higher education (Maringe and Gibbs, 2009)

IX. LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

Despite the contribution of the study to the area of International Universities for higher education in Nepal, the following potential limitations are to be considered. This research is not without limitations as it relied on a small

sample obtained. The research findings are based on the data collected through the convenience sampling method which mainly incorporates data from the students in Kathmandu Valley and the other major cities of Nepal. Though it will cover the target market for students seeking international degrees, the data collected might not be enough to depict the thought of everyone as a sample of the population surveyed. The findings therefore may not be generalized to all possible students seeking International Universities for higher education in Nepal.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This study has practical relevance for researchers, institutions and marketing practitioners. Based on the above findings, which indicated that the major focus should be on the quality of education and career prospects, higher education institutions should conduct further research on knowing the needs and expectations of the students and ensure that they are met. Further feedbacks are to be taken from the students currently studying in International Universities in order to further enhance the student's experience and improve visibility in the domestic market.

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